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Millennial-scale fingerprint of macroalgae in Arctic marine sediments

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Macroalgal genes present in up to 2600-year-old Greenland marine sediments at 60–79°N.
- Permanence and stability of macroalgal carbon in Arctic sediments
- Brown algae dominate the buried macroalgae with no clear link to shifting climate.
- Ancient sediment DNA (*sedaDNA*) analyzed on dated sediments with climate proxies.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Macroalgae are the most widely distributed marine vegetated habitats and contribute to marine carbon cycling and storage but with limited empirical documentation of long-term burial. To evaluate long-term burial of macroalgal-derived carbon in Arctic sediments, we analyzed eDNA from six dated sediment cores from off the coast of West Greenland (79°N–60°N). We applied metabarcoding of 18S rRNA genes to selected sediment layers covering the past ~2600 years, assessed spatio-temporal patterns of macroalgal taxa, and evaluated climatic drivers of macroalgal change using proxies for past sea surface conditions. Macroalgal DNA was present in all cores and 86.5 % of samples. Orders of brown algal (Laminariales, Fucales) were more prevalent than red or green orders and we found no consistent changes in the identity of macroalgal taxa, despite significant changes in sea surface conditions (temperature, sea ice, salinity) over this period. However, locally, we observed a significant decline in richness of macroalgal taxa buried over the last c. 800 years (Qeqertarsuup Tunua, Disko Bay). This decline coincided with the onset of the Little Ice Age and greater fluctuations in sea surface conditions. Overall, we demonstrate that macroalgae can be preserved for millennia in marine sediments along Greenland's

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west coast, documenting that macroalgae contribute to long-term carbon burial in the Arctic although their quantitative significance is still unknown.

1. Introduction

Macroalgal beds are the most widely distributed marine vegetated habitats on the globe (Duarte et al., 2022) and their vast production contributes to marine carbon (C) cycling and storage but there is still limited empirical documentation of their long-term burial and spatio-temporal burial patterns (Krause-Jensen and Duarte, 2016; Howard et al., 2023). This is especially the case in the Arctic region where data on marine biota is particularly scarce (Wassmann et al., 2011; Krause-Jensen et al., 2020).

In contrast to rooted marine vegetation, such as seagrasses, salt-marshes, and mangroves, which grow on soft and sandy seafloor and accumulate C in the sediments below them (Duarte et al., 2013; Macreadie et al., 2021), macroalgae mainly grow on rocky substrate where sediments do not accumulate, but they export part of their production to C sinks beyond their habitat, where it is challenging to trace (Hill et al., 2015; Krause-Jensen and Duarte, 2016; Howard et al., 2023; Filbee-Dexter et al., 2024). Over the past decade, key mechanisms and pathways for macroalgal C sequestration have been explored, including the burial of particulate organic C from macroalgae in marine sediments, and associated management potentials and limitations (Raven, 2017; Hurd et al., 2022; Pessarrodona et al., 2023; Ross et al., 2023). Nevertheless, there is still only limited direct evidence of macroalgal contribution to long-term C burial in marine sediments.

A variety of sedimentary analyses can be applied to trace C sources in marine sediments, e.g., C:N ratios, stable isotopes, lipids, polysaccharides, fossil assemblages, and other preserved biological compounds (Geraldini et al., 2019; Salmeán et al., 2022; Dahl et al., 2024). Environmental DNA (eDNA) is an emerging approach to fingerprint C sources in C reservoirs (Ortega et al., 2019; Queirós et al., 2019; Frigstad et al., 2021), including ancient sedimentary DNA (*sedDNA*) of deep sediment dating thousands of years back. Although the majority of sediment DNA represents living microorganisms, a small part of *sedDNA* is from long-dead organisms, including macroalgae. *SedaDNA* analyses were first used in lake sediments to identify bacterial remains (Coolen and Overmann, 1998) and later to identify eukaryotic remains in permafrost (Willerslev et al., 2003) and in marine sediments (Boere et al., 2009). Combined with dating of marine sediment cores, analyses of *sedDNA* are used to reconstruct the history of marine ecosystems over millennial time scales (Balint et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2023; Crump, 2021).

SedaDNA therefore also offers a novel approach to identify groups of organisms that contribute to long-term C burial in marine sediments and to reconstruct past sources of C sequestration (Wesselmann et al., 2021; Anglès d'Auriac et al., 2021). Reconstructions of ecosystems and physical environmental conditions from paleontological records further enable studies on potential impacts of past fluctuations in climate on past marine ecosystems (Balint et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2023) and C sequestration (Hein et al., 2017; Rantala et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2024). Such findings also underpin predictions of potential impacts of future climate on marine ecosystems (Epp, 2019), and associated C sequestration.

Recent eDNA studies have documented the prevalence of macroalgal-derived C in surface sediments around Greenland and Svalbard (Ørberg et al., 2022; Ørberg et al., 2023). However, there is no empirical evidence of long-term burial of macroalgal-derived C in Arctic marine sediments or of long-term changes in such burial, which could potentially reflect macroalgal responses to past changes in climate. Because the dominant macroalgal species in the Arctic have a boreal origin (Müller et al., 2009), warming is likely to stimulate their northward expansion as well as their productivity while also affecting light

availability at the seafloor through the combined effect of longer open water periods and increasing turbidity from runoff as the cryosphere melts (Krause-Jensen et al., 2020; Assis et al., 2022; Lebrun et al., 2022). *SedaDNA* analyses of macroalgal sequences in deep Arctic sediment cores could potentially document storage as shown for temperate marine sediments, dating 400 years back (Anglès d'Auriac et al., 2021; O'Dell, 2022).

Arctic macroalgae may have responded to the significant climate variability over the Holocene, driven by changes in ocean and atmospheric circulation in the Northern Hemisphere, including West Greenland (Axford et al., 2021). Around 3000 years ago, following the mid-Holocene warm period, the West Greenland Ice Sheet began to expand, reflecting the onset of millennial-scale cooling superimposed by shorter-term multidecadal to centennial fluctuations (e.g., Funder and Fredskild, 1989; Koç et al., 1993; Seidenkrantz et al., 2007, 2008; Hansen et al., 2020; Allan et al., 2021; Kjær et al., 2022). These changes influenced marine conditions off West Greenland, altering the balance between cold, low-salinity Polar water and warmer, saltier Atlantic water in the West Greenland Current. Periods of cold European climate were generally associated with strengthened Atlantic inflow to west Greenland, linked to subpolar gyre weakening. However, surface water conditions were often partly disabled from this pattern with more extensive sea-ice formation and transport during the European cold periods. Thus, during the Dark Ages Cold Period (450 to 650 CE) and the Little Ice Age (1250 to 1900 CE), subsurface and even near-surface waters in Southwestern and Southeastern Greenland were relatively warm (Kjær et al., 2022; Ogilvie and Jónsson, 2001; Seidenkrantz et al., 2007; Andresen et al., 2013, 2017), while the surface waters were cold and sea-ice cover was extensive (Seidenkrantz et al., 2007; Sha et al., 2017; Kuijpers et al., 2014; Miles et al., 2020). During the Roman Warm Period (50 BCE to 450 CE) and the Medieval Climate Anomaly (650–1050 CE) on the other hand, subsurface waters were cool, but sea ice was diminished (Seidenkrantz et al., 2008). These changes in climate regimes off West Greenland likely affected Arctic macroalgal production and, hence, the associated contribution to C storage through detrital transport and sequestration pathways, potentially being stimulated in warmer periods.

Here we use presence-absence data for macroalgal DNA through dated sediment cores along Greenland's Westcoast as a proxy for macroalgal carbon burial, acknowledging that differential DNA preservation, sediment mixing and degradation biases affect the macroalgal fingerprint in the sediment. We test the hypotheses that 1) macroalgal C is sequestered for long timescales (>100 years) in Arctic marine sediments, and 2) that long-term patterns in macroalgal fingerprints in the sediments may correlate with long term changes in climatic conditions. We do so based on *sedDNA* metabarcoding of six dated marine sediment cores from Greenland's west coast (Table 1). We investigate spatio-temporal patterns in macroalgal C burial by assessing richness, community composition and turnover of macroalgal taxa identified in the sediment cores. Finally, based on comparison with existing paleo-environmental data from these and neighboring sediment cores as well as new analyses of total organic carbon (TOC), sediment density, and bulk stable isotopes, we evaluate potential effects of past sea-surface conditions on macroalgal taxa identified in the Arctic sediment archives examined here.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study region and study sites

The study region covered a latitudinal range from 60°N to 79°N off

Table 1

List of marine sediment cores sampled for *sedaDNA* and/or used for paleo-environmental data, including associated collection data, references, dating method, and their application in this study. References to previous studies presenting age models and/or proxy-based paleo-environmental data used in the statistical analyses are also given. Cores analyzed for *sedaDNA* are indicated by *.

Region	Core ID	Position (DD)	Application	Corer method	Collection year	Depth (m) sampling site	Core length (cm)	Core missing top	Original reference	Age-model (reference)	Quantitative environmental data (method, reference)
Kane Basin	AMD14-Kane2B*	79.519; –70.888117	<i>sedaDNA</i> & Climate proxies	Calypso Square (CASQ)	2014	217	425	4 cm	Georgiadis et al., 2018	Radiocarbon & ²¹⁰ Pb (Georgiadis et al., 2018)	SST, Salinity, Sea-ice cover, Sea-ice concentration (MAT, Caron et al., 2019)
Melville Bay	AMD14-210*	75.40528; –61.65595	<i>sedaDNA</i>	Calypso Square (CASQ)	2014	1155	596	NA	Caron et al., 2019	Radiocarbon (Caron et al., 2019)	NA
Upernavik	AMD14-204	73.26105; –57.899783	Climate proxies for AMD14 210	Calypso Square (CASQ)	2014	987	734	NA	Caron et al., 2019	Radiocarbon (Caron et al., 2019)	SST, Salinity, Sea-ice cover, Sea-ice concentration (MAT, Caron et al., 2019)
Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay)	ACDC2014-03*	69.313; –51.3305	<i>sedaDNA</i>	Rumohr lot corer	2014	380	173	NA	Wangner et al., 2018	Radiocarbon & ²¹⁰ Pb (Wangner et al., 2018)	NA
Sullorsuaq Strait (Vaigat Strait)	DA06-139G	70.091433; –52.893083	Climate proxies for ACDC2014-03	Gravity corer	2006	384	446	NA	Dalhoff and Kuijpers, 2007	Radiocarbon (Andresen et al., 2011)	SST, Salinity, Sea-ice cover, Sea-ice concentration (MAT, Andresen et al., 2011 ; Sha et al., 2014)
Sisimiut Deep (Holsteinsborg Dyb)	GA306-GC3*	66.62472; –54.20972	<i>sedaDNA</i> & Climate proxies	Gravity core	2006	425	440	28 cm	Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013	Radiocarbon combined with ²¹⁰ Pb from box core (Erbs-Hansen et al., 2013)	Sea-ice concentration April (Diatom-based transfer function, Sha et al., 2017)
Nuuk Shelf	SA13-ST3-20G*	64.44571; –52.79414	<i>sedaDNA</i> & Climate proxies	Gravity corer	2013	498	587	18 cm	Seidenkrantz et al., 2013	Radiocarbon combined with ²¹⁰ Pb from Rumohr lot core (Allan et al., 2021)	SST, Salinity, Sea-ice cover, Sea-ice concentration (MAT, Allan et al., 2021)
Igaliku Fjord	PO 243-451*	60.69933; –46.03333	<i>sedaDNA</i> & Climate (qualitative)	Gravity corer	1998	304	351	NA	Hoffmann et al., 1999	Radiocarbon combined with ²¹⁰ Pb from box core (Roncaglia and Kuijpers, 2004 ; Jensen et al., 2004)	NA

the coast of West Greenland. The marine environment in this region is today affected by both cold and warmer waters. The relatively warm West Greenland Current is found at subsurface levels, and it consists of the combined flow of cold Polar Water from the Arctic Ocean, traveling southwards with the East Greenland Current along East Greenland, and warmer and saltier Atlantic Water from the Irminger Current flowing

below the Polar Water (Buch and Nielsen, 2001; Cuny et al., 2002; Tang et al., 2004; Curry et al., 2011; Azetsu-Scott et al., 2012). This warmer water is overlain by local meltwater from the ice sheet (Buch and Nielsen, 2001).

Our study included six main sites along the 19 degrees latitude gradient (Fig. 1). Each main site was represented by an archived long

Fig. 1. a) Sediment core sampling sites along Greenland’s west coast and bar plots b–g showing macroalgal taxa richness at order level detected with *sedDNA* in six dated sediment cores (b → g = North → South). Note that the scales of the y-axes (Years CE (Common Era)) are discrete and differ between sediment cores (see associated sediment slice depth to Years CE in Supplementary Table 1). In the bar plot (d) from Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay) cold (gray) and warm (white) climate regimes are marked (This climate data is from the literature and based on other cores from the Qeqertarsuup Tunua region).

marine sediment core sampled for eDNA metabarcoding, subsequently referred to as *sedDNA*, and associated variables (Table 1). Two additional cores neighboring two of the main sites were included for supplementary information on climate- and environmental proxies to yield a total of eight sediment cores (Table 1).

The cores were collected during six independent research cruises conducted between 1998 and 2014. The cores were sampled at water depths ranging from 217 m to 1155 m and their length ranged from 173 cm to 734 cm (Table 1). The sediments of the cores consist of olive green to gray mud. References to previous paleoenvironmental analyses performed on the cores are provided in Table 1.

2.2. Sampling from archived sediment cores

The six main cores had been halved and stored in the dark at 4 °C in marine sediment archives. We visited these archives and subsampled selected sediment layers for analysis of *sedDNA*, density, TOC, and bulk stable isotope composition (Supplementary Table S1). None of the core halves, except core GA306-GC3 from a deep trench off Sisimiut (Holsteinsborg Dyb) (Table 1), had been subsampled prior to sampling for this study. The Nuuk Shelf core (SA13-ST3-20G) and the Qeqertarsuup Tunua core (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03) were subsampled shortly after core retrieval and *sedDNA* samples were stored frozen until used in this study. We sampled at a distance of at least 2 cm from the core liner periphery to avoid contamination from other sediment layers during penetration of the corer instrument.

For density, TOC, and bulk stable isotope analyses, we sampled 2 cm³ of the exposed sediment layer into zip lock bags using a sterile cut-off 5 ml plastic syringe. With a new, sterile cut-off 5 ml syringe, we collected an additional 2–4 cm³ of sediment into 15 ml vials for *sedDNA* analyses. We added RNAlater to the 15 ml vials (volume equivalent to the sample collected) and mixed thoroughly by inversion. All samples were stored immediately after sampling at 4 °C until further analyses. Syringes, spatulas, and benches were sterilized with 10 % bleach in milliQ water, gloves were always used during subsampling and changed regularly. For the top section (0–50 cm) of the Sisimiut core (GA306-GC3), we sampled from previously freeze-dried material stored in zip lock bags using sterile spatulas. The previous handling of the freeze-dried material had not used sterile procedures. We did not obtain samples for density, TOC, and stable isotope analyses from the Qeqertarsuup Tunua core (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03) or from the upper part (0–49 cm) of the Sisimiut Deep core. For the Nuuk Shelf core (SA13-ST3-20G), TOC data were available without isotopic analysis and density (Pelikan et al., 2019), so these were not included.

2.3. Density, TOC, and bulk stable isotope analyses

For calculating density (dry weight per volume), a known volume (c. 2 ml) of wet sediment was weighed, dried at 60 °C, and re-weighed. Using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Flash 2000-Organic Elemental Analyzer 2014), we analyzed the samples for TOC content and stable isotope composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) of the bulk organic matter after acid treatment (Kennedy et al., 2005, see below). We compared the isotopic signature of core samples with the isotopic range of primary producers relevant for West Greenland (macroalgae, eelgrass (*Zostera marina*), terrestrial plants and phytoplankton-particulate organic matter (P-POM) data obtained from Ørberg et al. (2023) and references therein). We calculated the organic carbon (OC) density for each sample by the product of TOC and density. Prior to analysis, sediment samples were dried at 60 °C, crushed with a mortar and treated with acid to eliminate carbonate to represent the organic material only (Kennedy et al., 2005). We added 20 μl 1 M HCL to the dried and crushed samples weighed out in a double silver capsule (20–30 mg) and if there were bubbles, we added another 20 μl 1 M HCL until the bubbling stopped, to ensure that all carbonates were removed. After acidification, sediment samples were re-dried at 60 °C.

2.4. Sedimentary ancient DNA (*sedDNA*) analyses

We extracted DNA from 0.25 to 0.35 g of wet sediment using a published method for marine sediments (Kjeldsen et al., 2007). We included one extraction blank for every batch of extractions (12–24 samples), which were performed in an area of the laboratory physically separated from other types of molecular work. Benches and instruments were cleaned with 10 % bleach and 70 % ethanol or RNaseZap (Invitrogen) before use to avoid contamination.

We targeted the 18S rRNA gene with the 18S-V7 PCR assay for the approximately 120 bp long V7 region (for detailed PCR protocol please see Supplementary Table S2). We prepared two 96-well plates for PCR and sequencing. The first plate included samples from core SA13-ST3-20G from the Nuuk shelf (Supplementary Table S1). The second plate included the remaining samples from core AMD14-Kane2B, AMD14-210, ACDC201-1-03, PO243-451 and GA306-GC3 (Supplementary Table S1). PCR reactions contained 5 μl of QIAGEN Multiplex PCR Master Mix, 1 μl (1.0 μM) of each primer, 1 μl of DNA template, and 2 μl of high purity PCR water. We performed five replicate PCR assays per sample (five different 96 well plates). PCR blanks (DNA-free water) and extraction blanks were run in each PCR batch. The five PCR assay replicates were pooled to reduce PCR bias and then visualized on 2 % agarose gel to ensure successful amplification and the expected amplicon size. Illumina Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation protocol (Illumina) was followed to clean and add indexes to the amplicons (2nd PCR) to distinguish samples after pooling and sequencing. We sequenced four extraction blanks and two PCR blanks from the first plate with Nuuk shelf samples, and five extraction blanks and one PCR blank from the second plate with the remaining samples. Sequencing was conducted on an Illumina platform (MiSeq) at KAUST Biological Core Lab with the Illumina MiSeq Reagent kit v3 (600 cycles).

The Illumina MiSeq sequencing output was demultiplexed using the Illumina protocol and assays were trimmed using Cutadapt 1.17 with default settings (Martin, 2011). The sequenced reads were assessed and filtered following default settings of the DADA2 1.8.0 pipeline in R (Callahan et al., 2016; R Core Team, 2020). The reads were quality-filtered, and forward- and reverse reads shorter than 90 bp were removed. The reads were then dereplicated, sequencing errors were corrected, and the forward and reverse reads were merged, forming sequence variants (SVs). Taxonomy was assigned with default settings (assignTaxonomy function), except for minboot, which was set at a more conservative value (70). We assigned taxonomy using a curated SILVA database (Yilmaz et al., 2014) and a recently developed barcode database of North Atlantic and Arctic macroalgal species from Ørberg et al. (2022) (NCBI accession numbers: MK453128-MK453194, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). Following the recommendation for taxonomic resolution on macroalgae with the applied assay, we identified SVs to order level (Ørberg et al., 2022).

To identify potential contaminants originating from extraction, PCR or tag-jumps, we used the ‘decontam’ R package (isContaminant function) (Davis et al., 2018). For this we applied the frequency method, which identifies contaminants by frequency that varies inversely with sample DNA concentration of initial extractions. We evaluated different probability thresholds and chose 0.3 and 0.2 for the first plate (Nuuk Shelf, core SA13-ST3-20G) and second plate (with the remaining samples), respectively. The identified contaminants were removed before further data analyses. In addition, we removed SVs with 3 reads or less as often done when analyzing ancient sedimentary DNA (Capo et al., 2021; Curtin et al., 2021).

We assessed rarefaction curves and accumulation curves and decided not to rarefy the sequence data since we use presence-absence data and did not want to remove presence of species (Supplementary, Figs. S1–S4). Instead, we plotted SV richness and read depth (library size) per sample to evaluate whether the number of SVs was generally lower in samples with lower read depths compared to samples with higher read depth. If so, we set a threshold for the read depth to remove

samples where a low read depth may have resulted in low SV richness.

The sequence results from one sample (slice depth 77 cm – Nuuk Shelf, core SA13-ST3-20G) were excluded because the number of reads was too low (we set a threshold of minimum 40,000 reads per sample for the first plate, while we did not introduce a threshold on the second plate; Supplementary, Figs. S7–S10). Also, the bioinformatic decontamination procedure resulted in the removal of 79 out of total 5270 SVs from the Nuuk Shelf core of which none were classified as macroalgal taxa. In the second plate with the remaining sediment core samples, 462 SVs out of a total of 7742 SVs were removed and 8 of these SVs were classified as macroalgal taxa.

2.5. Chronology and paleo-environmental data of sediment cores

We used existing, mainly published but also some unpublished, paleo-environmental data on sea-surface conditions (i.e. sea-ice cover and concentration, sea-surface temperature and salinity, and primary productivity) from the six sampled cores and the two additional cores (eight in total, see Table 1).

Available age models from all the eight marine sediment cores were included, although only six cores were sampled for *sedDNA*. Because quantitative data on past sea-surface conditions was missing from two of the *sedDNA*-analyzed cores (Melville Bay: AMD14-210 and Igaliku Fjord: PO243-451), we supported the statistical analyses with paleo-environmental data from two neighboring cores (Table 1). For Melville Bay (core AMD14-210) we used quantitative paleo-environmental data from the shelf off Upernavik Fjord (core AMD14-204) (Fig. 4 in Caron et al., 2019), while for Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03) we used quantitative paleo-environmental data from Sullorsuaq Strait (Vaigat Strait; core DA06-139G) (Andresen et al., 2011) (Table 1).

In five of the six *sedDNA*-analyzed cores, the age models were based on a combination of calibrated radiocarbon-dating (^{14}C) of calcareous foraminifera and ^{210}Pb -measurements of sediment from the same core or an associated box core collected at the same site (Table 1), while in the remaining *sedDNA*-analyzed core (Melville Bay, core AMD14-210) plus the two supporting cores (Upernavik, core AMD14-204, and Sullorsuaq Strait, core DA06-139), the age models were alone based on radiocarbon-dating (^{14}C) of calcareous foraminifera or seaweed fragments. For some of the cores, very low ^{210}Pb -activities suggested a loss of the top sediments during the core retrieval (Table 1). For details on the age models please see the original studies listed in Table 1.

Because sediment DNA reflects local to regional-scale deposition, we explored potential relationships between *sedDNA* and large-scale environmental conditions reflected in the chronology of the sedimentary archives. The paleo-environmental data used in comparison with the *sedDNA* data was retrieved using proxy data, which provides indirect information on the past environmental conditions, and in this case past sea-surface conditions. Different paleo-environmental data were available for the various cores, and for consistency, only the dinoflagellate-based MAT (modern analogue technique) records and the diatom-based sea-ice concentration were used in the statistical analyses, while other published paleo-environmental information was brought into the discussion. The *sedDNA* samples and paleo-environmental data were matched by the core ages derived from age models (see references in Table 1) with an accepted offset of maximum 25 years, which is within the margin of error for geological dating of cores.

The modern analogue technique (MAT) provides quantitative estimates of summer and winter sea-surface temperature, summer and winter sea-surface salinity, sea-ice cover in percentage and concentration, as well as summer, winter and annual primary production based on the downcore distribution of dinoflagellate cysts, which have been compared with the assemblages found in modern surface samples at 1968 sites (de Vernal et al., 2020). The technique has been used on cores DA06-139G (for original data see Andresen et al., 2011), AMD14-204 (Fig. 4 in Caron et al., 2019), AMD14-Kane2B (Fig. 6 in Caron et al.,

2019), and SA13-ST3-20G (Allan et al., 2021). Diatom and foraminiferal assemblages as well as biomarker records were also available for core AMD14-204 (Hansen et al., 2020; Limoges et al., 2020), and organic sea-ice biomarker data combined with the distribution of benthic foraminifera were also available for core AMD14-Kane2B. For PO243-451 benthic foraminiferal and diatom-based data were available (Lassen et al., 2004; Jensen et al., 2004). The assemblage distribution of diatom species provides information on sea-surface temperature and sea-ice cover, while assemblages of benthic foraminifera inform about conditions at the sea floor, although in both cases the analyses are qualitative. The analyses of organic sea-ice biomarkers ((P)IP25, IP25 and HBI III) measured on the sediment give qualitative information on sea-ice concentrations. If the downcore diatom assemblages show sufficient similarity with modern conditions, a transfer function analysis may be carried out, where conditions in similar modern sites are used to calculate past conditions. We used a diatom-based transfer function analysis providing a reconstruction of past changes in sea-ice concentration for core GA306-GC3 (for original data see: Sha et al., 2017). For core ACDC2014-03, reconstructions of water mass distribution in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay) and icebergs from Sermeq Kujalleq were available from analyses of benthic foraminiferal assemblages and the presence of ice-rafted debris (IRD), respectively (Wangner et al., 2018).

2.6. Statistical analyses of temporal and environmental drivers

We calculated macroalgal richness and community change variables such as turnover, mean rank shifts in each *sedDNA* core at the order level. Change was assessed as the difference between two consecutive down-core sampling points and was analyzed using turnover, rank shift and rate change functions, in the ‘codyn’ R package (Hallett et al., 2016). We calculated all three metrics of turnover (total, disappearances and appearances). Analyses were done at the order level because we were interested in changes in key macroalgal groups, and because the PCR amplified and sequenced 18S rRNA gene region did not allow high taxonomic resolution.

To evaluate environmental and temporal effects on the various community change variables and taxa (order) richness, we fitted generalized linear models (glm function, ‘stats’ R package), multiple linear models, including mixed effect models to account for spatial variation (lmer/glmer function, ‘lme4’ R package, Bates et al., 2015), or generalized additive models for non-linear relationships (gam function, ‘mgcv’ R package, Wood et al., 2016). We used a generalized additive model to evaluate temporal changes in taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay) because the general assumptions for a linear model were not met (Supplementary, Figs. S5–S6). In the mixed effect models, we added the collection site of cores as a random effect, to reduce potential patterns related to spatial variation. We assessed collinearity between explanatory variables using Pearson’s correlation test and only included the most ecologically relevant variable in the models for which Pearson’s correlation >0.7 . We evaluated the assumptions of linearity, normality, and homoscedasticity through residual and Q-Q plots. When fitting models for taxa richness, we assumed a Poisson distribution and tested for overdispersion.

In addition, we performed distance-based redundancy analyses (dbRDA) to evaluate environmental and temporal effects on macroalgal community composition in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (capscale function, ‘vegan’ R package, Oksanen et al., 2022) based on order level. Jaccard distances were calculated for the presence-absence community matrix of macroalgal taxa. All continuous environmental variables were standardized prior to the analyses. In addition, we performed partial dbRDA’s to evaluate potential drivers of community composition in West Greenland overall, and partialled-out the spatial effect of collection site. A permutational ANOVA-like test was performed to assess the significance of the dbRDA models, its axes and environmental predictors after 999 permutations.

3. Results

3.1. Macroalgal DNA is preserved for millennia in Arctic marine sediments

We detected preserved macroalgal DNA in all six marine sediment cores along a N-S gradient (79°-60°N) off the West Coast of Greenland dating as far as ~2600 years back (Fig. 1). Although macroalgal reads constituted only a minor fraction of the total reads, we detected macroalgal DNA in 86.5 % of the analyzed samples (n = 89), even in the

oldest one, from Melville Bay (core AMD14-210) c. year 640 BCE (before Current Era) (Fig. 1c). There was no clear N-S gradient in taxa richness. Both the highest taxa richness (10 orders at c.1810 CE) and highest mean taxa richness (mean ± SE, 5.7 ± 1.52) of macroalgae were detected in Igaliku Fjord (core PO243-451), the southernmost site, followed by Melville Bay (core AMD14-210) (4.5 ± 1.30), the second-northernmost site. The lowest mean taxa richness was detected on the Nuuk shelf (core SA13-ST3-20G) (1.4 ± 0.41) followed by Sisimiut Deep (Holsteinsborg Dyb, core GA306-GC3) (1.7 ± 0.47), representing the second- and third-southernmost location. Kane Basin (core AMD14-Kane2B) in the North

Fig. 2. Bulk stable isotope signals ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) and organic carbon density of sediment samples from four of the sediment cores. a) Iso-plot with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signals of sediment core samples (empty) and reference material (filled). P-POM = Phytoplankton-Particulate Organic Matter. b) Organic carbon density and c) $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signature per slice depth in four sediment cores.

and Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay, core ACDC2014-03) centrally on the West Coast had intermediate levels of mean taxa richness (2.8 ± 0.81 and 3.3 ± 0.64 , respectively).

Targeting the 18S rRNA gene, we identified eight red algal orders (class Florideophyceae), four brown algal orders (class Phaeophyceae), and one green algal order (class Ulvophyceae) (Fig. 1). The most prevalent macroalgal order across space and time was Laminariales followed by Fucales (both brown algae), which were detected in all six cores (Fig. 1) and in 73 % and 60 % of the samples, respectively. Laminariales was detected even in the oldest sediment layers, which was c. year 20 CE on the Nuuk shelf (core SA13-ST3-20G) (Fig. 1f) and of Fucales at c. 640 years BCE in Melville Bay (core AMD14-210) (Fig. 1c). In only one core from the southernmost site (Igaliku Fjord, core PO243-451), we found Laminariales in all the sediment samples dating from c. 950–2000 years CE (Fig. 1g). The third most prevalent macroalgal order was Ceramiales (red algae) found in 44.3 % of the samples and in all six cores (Fig. 1). The rarest order overall was the red algal order, Ahnfeltiales, which was only detected in the two northernmost cores, Kane Basin (core AMD14-Kane2B) and Melville Bay (core AMD14-210), at c. 430 years CE and at

c. 690 years CE, respectively (Fig. 1b, c).

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ isotopic signature of organic matter in the Kane Basin, Sisimiut Deep, and Igaliku Fjord sediment cores showed strong resemblance with macroalgae (Fig. 2a), while the signature of the Melville Bay core resembled that of P-POM (phytoplankton) (Fig. 2a). While the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signals were consistent downcore for the Sisimiut Deep, Igaliku Fjord, and Melville Bay cores, the Kane Basin core varied between -13 and -20 downcore (Fig. 2c). The acidification treatment (to eliminate inorganic C) prior to the stable isotope analysis was slower for the Kane Basin samples compared to the other core samples, meaning that the Kane Basin core contained considerably more inorganic C compared to the other core samples. Also, the densities of OC in the Kane Basin core samples were generally higher (0.02 to $0.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) compared to the other core samples (maximum $0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) (Fig. 2b). The cores from Melville Bay, Sisimiut Deep, and Igaliku Fjord displayed higher OC densities in the uppermost sediment layers compared to the deeper sediment layers, while the Kane Basin core displayed lower OC densities in the uppermost layers compared to deeper layers (Fig. 2b).

Table 2

Statistical tests of temporal and environmental effects on macroalgal community measures (Richness = order richness, Community = community composition and Total turnover = order turnover) obtained from *seDNA* analyses of dated sediment cores along the west coast of Greenland. GAM = generalized additive model, GLM = generalized linear model, GLMM = generalized linear mixed effect model, dbrDA = Distance-based redundancy analysis. All generalized models were run with Poisson as the log link function.

Regions	N	Model	Coefficients	Estimate	SE	t	p-Value
a)	88	GLMM – Richness	<i>Intercept</i>	1.075	0.2007	5.356	8.5e–08***
Kane Basin			Year:Core	–0.1182	0.0624	–1.895	0.058
Melville Bay	77	Partial dbrDA – Community	Year:Core		Sum of sqrs	0.6467	0.784
Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay)					0.1435		
Sisimiut Deep (Holsteinsborg Dyb)							
Nuuk Shelf							
Igaliku Fjord							
b)	27	GAM – Richness	<i>Intercept</i>	1.07	0.1191	9.015	<2e–16***
Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay) with environmental variables from Sullorsuaq Strait (Vaigat Strait)			Year	edf = 2.375	ref.df = 2.93	Chi.sqr = 20.68	0.00014***
	22	GLM – Richness	<i>Intercept</i>	1.190	0.1297	9.172	<2e–16***
			Year	–0.3285	0.1175	–2.795	0.0052**
			SeaIceConc	0.4981	0.3197	1.558	0.11920
			PSUsummer	0.5488	0.3166	1.733	0.08301
			PrimProd	0.2100	0.2144	0.979	0.32741
	21	dbrDA – Community			Sum of sqrs		
			Year		0.42705	2.3621	0.034*
			SeaIceConc		0.03773	0.2087	0.974
			PSUsummer		0.16840	0.9314	0.462
			PrimProd		0.27981	1.5477	0.164
c)	47	GLMM – Richness	<i>Intercept</i>	0.955	0.19634	4.864	1.15e–06***
Kane Basin			Year:Core	–0.12123	0.08623	–1.406	0.160
Melville Bay (with environmental variables from Upernavik)			SeaIceConc:	0.21528	0.31264	0.689	0.491
Qeqertarsuup Tunua (with environmental variables from Sullorsuaq Strait)			Core				
Nuuk Shelf			PSUwinter:	0.10207	0.14179	0.720	0.472
			Core				
			Tsummer:	0.05201	0.36028	0.144	0.885
			Core				
	40	LMM – Total turnover	<i>Intercept</i>	0.107	0.2328	0.459	0.705
			Year:Core	–0.2000	0.1674	–1.195	0.240
			SeaIceConc:	0.4069	0.2543	1.600	0.198
			Core				
			PSUwinter:	0.1304	0.1850	0.705	0.488
			Core				
			Tsummer:	0.2386	0.2798	0.853	0.430
			Core				
	43	Partial dbrDA – Community	<i>intercept</i>		Sum of sqrs		
			Year:Core		0.3580	1.7266	0.100
			SeaIceConc:		0.0640	0.3089	0.976
			Core				
			PSUwinter:		0.2886	1.3921	0.209
			Core				
			Tsummer:		0.3436	1.6571	0.121
			Core				

Signif. codes: 0 <= ***<0.001 **<0.01 *<0.05

3.2. Temporal patterns of macroalgal DNA in Arctic marine sediments

We observed relatively low rates of macroalgal order-level community change at the individual sites, together spanning up to c. 2600 years (Supplementary, Fig. S14). The maximum rates of community change were found on the shelf off Nuuk (slope = 0.055; core SA13-ST3-20G) and in the Kane Basin (slope = 0.045; core AMD14-Kane2B). In the

Kane Basin core, macroalgal taxa were absent in consecutive samples dated c. year 1500 CE to c. year 1800 CE followed by a re-appearance of 6 different orders in the youngest sample from year 1900 CE (Fig. 1). A similar pattern was observed on the shelf off Nuuk with the absence of macroalgal taxa in consecutive samples dated c. year 1000 CE to approximately 1200 CE followed by the re-appearance of taxa c. 1300 CE. The switch between presence and absence of macroalgae between

Fig. 3. Macroalgal taxa richness over the past 2000 years in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03) based on *sedDNA* at order level and the estimated smoother for Year CE in generalized additive model for order richness (Table 2b, GAM, $p = 0.00014$, $n = 27$, $edf = 2.375$).

time periods generated the high turnover observed in this core.

Overall, we did not identify significant changes over time in any of the macroalgal order-level community change variables (taxa turnover, mean rank shifts), richness (GLMM, Table 2a), nor community composition (partial dbRDA, Table 2a), the latter reflecting the dominant taxa. Only in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03), we found statistically significant temporal changes in both order-level richness and community composition (Fig. 3, GAM, GLM and dbRDA, Table 2b). Here, the changes in community composition over time were driven by the presence-absence of the orders Gigartinales, Ceramiales, Fucales, and Dictyotales (Supplementary, Fig. S15), although only 7 % ($R_{adj} = 0.07$) of the variation in community composition was explained by temporal changes. The temporal change in taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua, was described by a non-linear smoothed curve suggesting a relatively constant taxa richness from c. 100 years CE (core base) to c. 200 years CE, followed by a decline in taxa richness over the following c. 800 years until present (Fig. 3b). The data from Qeqertarsuup Tunua did not indicate an increase or decrease in mean rank shift or taxa turnover over time (Fig. 4) although, the past c. 600 years showed greater fluctuations in taxa turnover between consecutive samples compared to the prior c. 500 years, with slightly more disappearances than appearances

(Fig. 4a). This included the absence of the otherwise prevalent orders, Laminariales and Fucales, in four and six out of seven samples, respectively, that represent the past c. 100 years (Fig. 1d).

3.3. Environmental drivers of change in macroalgal DNA in Arctic marine sediments

The temporal resolution of available quantitative paleo-environmental data on sea-surface conditions from the investigated sediment cores was low for some of the cores. This was specifically the case in the Kane Basin core (AMD14-Kane2B), where a c. 2000-year period was represented by only six data points (Fig. 5).

In Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay), the temporal resolution of both paleo-environmental data and *seda*DNA data was rather good, with 43 and 27 data points, respectively, representing a ~1800-year period (Figs. 1, 5). Twenty-two of the *seda*DNA samples from Qeqertarsuup Tunua were matched with paleo-environmental data from a nearby sediment core (Sullorsuaq Strait, core DA06-139G). Core SA13-ST3-20G from the shelf off Nuuk also contained a comparatively high-resolution data set and with 12 out of 14 *seda*DNA samples from the Nuuk shelf matched with paleo-environmental data. In the remaining sediment

Fig. 4. Macroalgal community change variables (Taxa turnover (Turnover), Mean Rank Shift, Rate of community change (Euclidean distance, slope = 0.212)) of macroalgal taxa based on *seda*DNA from Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Disko Bay; core ACDC2014-03) spanning the past nearly 2000 years ($n = 27$).

Fig. 5. Past sea-surface conditions (paleo-environmental data) approximated from climate-proxies (MAT) in deep marine sediment cores from Greenland's west coast (Table 1 and Fig. 1 a), arranged here in a N->S gradient from left to right. The sea-ice concentration in Sisimiut was approximated by diatoms and not MAT. The red points mark the values which we could either directly (Kane basin = AMD14-Kane2B, Sisimiut (Holsteinsborg) = GA306-GC3 and Nuuk shelf = SA13-ST3-20G) or indirectly (Upernavik = AMD14-204, Sullorsuaq (Vaigat Strait in Disko Bay) = DA06-139G - marked with a square in Fig. 1a) align with the *sedDNA* samples and further use in the statistical analyses. Climate-proxies were not available from the cores AMD14-210 (Melville Bay), ACDC2014-03 (Qeqertarsuup Tunua, Disko Bay) and PO 243-451 (Igaliku Fjord).

cores, none or less than half of the *sedDNA* samples could be matched with paleo-environmental data (Fig. 5, red points, and Supplementary Fig. S13). Overall, 47 of the *sedDNA* samples were aligned with paleo-environmental data.

Some variables for surface conditions displayed collinearity in the overall dataset (Supplementary, Fig. S11) and therefore only sea-ice concentration, winter salinity, summer SST and years CE were included in the full models including all sediment core samples with paleo-environmental data available (Kane Basin, Melville Bay, Qeqertarsuup Tunua and Nuuk Shelf; $n = 47$). In this overall model, we found no significant effect of surface conditions on macroalgal taxa richness, turnover, or community composition (GLMM and partial dBRDA, Table 2c). We could not fit a model to mean rank shift due to problems of singularity in the model.

In Qeqertarsuup Tunua, two consecutive time periods (c. 750–1500 years CE and c. 1500–2000 years CE) with comparatively low and high fluctuations in surface conditions, respectively (Fig. 5) coincided with a low versus high fluctuation in macroalgal taxa (turnover) (Fig. 4). Further, the significant decline in taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua over the past c. 800 years (i.e. since around year 1200 CE) (Fig. 3) partially overlapped with a recent period of greater fluctuations in surface conditions (c. 1500–2000 years CE) (Fig. 5). Nevertheless, our statistical analysis did not reveal any significant effect of past sea-surface conditions on macroalgal community composition or taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua sediments (GLM and dBRDA, Table 2b). We could

not fit a model to mean rank shift or taxa turnover in Qeqertarsuup Tunua because the assumptions for a parametric model were not met. Some of the variables for surface conditions displayed collinearity in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Supplementary, Fig. S15). Hence, we included only sea-ice concentration, summer salinity, primary production and years CE as explanatory variables for macroalgal community measures.

4. Discussion

4.1. Carbon sequestration of macroalgae in the Arctic

The six sediment cores from 60°N to 79°N off West Greenland showed a prevalent fingerprint of macroalgal DNA over the past ~2600 years. The genetic remains of macroalgae in most sediments >100 years old, including in the oldest sample analyzed (c. 640 BCE), prove that macroalgae, especially brown algae, are common C donors to Arctic sediments, although we cannot quantify their importance. The isotopic signature available from three of the sediment cores further supported the presence of macroalgal C in the sediments. Our study is the first to document the long-term conservation of macroalgal C in marine sediments in the Arctic, supporting earlier observations made from land-based cores (Pedersen and Bennike, 1993). The findings are an important supplement to those of Ørberg et al. (2023) who showed the prevalent fingerprint of macroalgae in Arctic surface sediments and thereby verified that macroalgae are transported to the surface of

potential C sink sites. We now show that their organic remains can be preserved at Millennial time scales in Arctic sediments.

Our findings confirm the potential of *sedaDNA* and metabarcoding to track the presence of macroalgae over centuries. These results supplement earlier findings of kelp *sedaDNA* in temperate sediment core samples about 400 years old (Anglès d'Auriac et al., 2021; O'Dell, 2022). One other study has used *sedaDNA* to relate historic changes in brown macroalgae with changes in coral communities (del Carmen Gomez Cabrera et al., 2019). The novelty of this study is that we combined *sedaDNA*-based assessment of macroalgae with paleo-environmental data on local sea-surface variables to assess drivers of macroalgae richness. *SedaDNA* not only allowed the detection of macroalgal taxa buried thousands of years ago but also gave us the possibility to explore drivers of historic changes. In contrast to previous studies on macroalga *sedaDNA*, we have evaluated the millennial-scale fingerprint of all three major groups of macroalgae. Earlier studies targeted surface sediments (Queirós et al., 2019; Queirós et al., 2023; Ørberg et al., 2022; Ørberg et al., 2023; Ortega et al., 2020; Hamaguchi et al., 2022; Bellgrove et al., 2023) and the water column (Ortega et al., 2019; Staehr et al., 2022) but not deep sediments. Even though brown algae are expected to be the largest macroalgal C donors to Arctic sediments, red algal-remains are prevalent throughout the world's deep oceans (Ortega et al., 2019) and preserved in Arctic sediments from the Early Holocene (Pedersen and Bennike, 1993). We found brown algal orders, Laminariales and Fucales, to be the most prevalent both geographically and temporally, but we also found a rather wide range of red algae orders, with Ceramiales being the third most prevalent order after the brown algae. This pattern matches that of marine surface sediments off Greenland, although in the surface sediments Ectocarpales was the most prevalent order followed by Laminariales, Fucales, and Ceramiales (Ørberg et al., 2023). Metabarcoding studies from other climate zones also report that red algae had a wider taxonomical range in surface sediments compared to brown and green algae (Ortega et al., 2020; Bellgrove et al., 2023).

We observed the greatest overall richness of taxa in our only fjord site, Igaliku Fjord, which was also the southernmost study site (Fig. 1). Macroalgal richness at the Melville Bay site was almost as high as at the fjord site. However, the other sites did not reflect any latitudinal pattern in sediment macroalgal richness when assessed by presence-absence of taxa. This lack of any clear N-S gradient in the long-term preservation of macroalgal assemblages in the six sediment cores off West Greenland indicates that local conditions such as distance from shore and current patterns override potential latitudinal effects along this wide latitude gradient. Indeed, the greater richness of taxa at the Igaliku Fjord site, could reflect higher richness in the macroalgal source communities within fjords and/or that this site was simply located closer to macroalgal source habitats. A dilution of detectable macroalgal DNA with water depth and increasing distance to the coast has been reported in other studies (Ørberg et al., 2023; Ortega et al., 2019; Bellgrove et al., 2023). Also, a majority of floating macroalgal detritus, mostly brown algae, are likely retained within Arctic fjord systems where they can potentially be sequestered. Hence, data from the Nuuk fjord system on Greenland's Westcoast indicated that 80 % of macroalgal detritus was retained in the fjord (Ager et al., 2023). This pattern may help explain the greater richness of taxa observed in Igaliku Fjord as opposed to the coastal sites (Fig. 1). Schimani et al. (2022) also observed major depositions of macroalgae on the seafloor of an Arctic fjord. Indeed, fjords are well-known hotspots of C burial because they receive and retain large amounts of organic material from the surroundings and therefore may serve as temporary storage site for OC between glacial periods in an icehouse climate (Smith et al., 2015). Based on macroalgal DNA as a proxy, our results suggest that macroalgae may contribute to such sedimentary OC storage around Greenland.

4.2. Drivers of change in macroalgal burial in Arctic sediments

The presence of macroalgal DNA in the sediments did not have a general temporal trend or obvious relationship with climate proxies through any of the *sedaDNA*-based parameters. In fact, temporal changes for each site were less than the differences between sites. However, we did observe spatial differences and at the site with the highest temporal sampling resolution (Qeqertarsuup Tunua; Disko Bay), we found a decline in taxa richness of macroalgae starting 800 years ago and lasting until the present (Fig. 1d). This also suggests that the lower temporal sampling resolution from the other sites may limit our ability to detect changes in macroalgal burial. In contrast to the Melville Bay, Sisimiut Deep, and Igaliku Fjord cores, the Kane Basin core displayed considerable variation in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ downcore, which could indicate high variation in C donors through time. It is also worth noting that the Kane Basin core samples contained more inorganic C compared to the other core samples, which could affect the isotopic measurements, either from higher amounts of acid residues left in the sample or leftover inorganic C after the acid treatment.

The decline in taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua, showed no significant relationship with regional sea-surface variables included in our analysis but coincided with greater fluctuations in regional sea-surface conditions. Contrary to the other sampling sites, the Qeqertarsuup Tunua *sedaDNA* sampling site is near a marine terminating glacier, which likely causes major physical and biological changes to the nearby environment as observed in other Arctic fjords (Meire et al., 2017). The environmental data from the sediment core in the northern part of the bay may not reflect the situation at the sampling site of the *sedaDNA* core, which is located further south in the bay closer to the glacier, perhaps explaining why our statistical analyses did not show any effect of past surface conditions on taxa richness. It is also possible that other abiotic and biotic parameters not included in this analysis affected taxa diversity as well as burial of macroalgal DNA. For example, siltation from run-off or glacial melting may increase turbidity in macroalgal habitats, lowering light penetration and macroalgal growth (Niedzwiedz and Bischof, 2023; Bartsch et al., 2016) or it may affect substrate suitability for recolonization (Moy and Christie, 2012). Shifts in kelp community structure are observed at other glacially impacted sites although with no change in species richness and standing biomass (Ronowicz et al., 2020). Finally, local changes in currents may affect the transport of macroalgal DNA, and grazing by sea urchins may also affect macroalgal distribution and detritus export (Filbee-Dexter et al., 2020).

Other environmental reconstructions from Qeqertarsuup Tunua of changes in the West Greenland Current show that the subsurface waters were quite warm around 0–1000 CE (Andresen et al., 2011; Wangner et al., 2018; Perner et al., 2013). The onset of the Little Ice Age around 1250 CE in Greenland (Miles et al., 2020) resulted in increased sea-ice formation in Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Allan et al., 2018; Sha et al., 2016) and changed the glacial configuration of Sermeq Kujalleq (Jakobshavn Isbræ) (Wangner et al., 2018). The cold climate and lowered surface melt on the Ice Sheet resulted in the formation of an ice tongue and thereby less iceberg calving. Reduced intensity of the subglacial plume results in decreased nutrient upwelling (Meire et al., 2015; Cape et al., 2019) and less siltation in the close vicinity of the glacier. Near the glacier in Qeqertarsuup Tunua, macroalgal productivity and associated delivery of macroalgal C to marine sediment deposits could have been negatively impacted by reduced temperatures and associated reduction in light penetration due to increased sea-ice formation (Allan et al., 2018) and reduced nutrient supply could also have played a role. Macroalgal studies along N-S climate gradients in Greenland suggests that the distribution of e.g. Laminariales and Fucales are limited by low temperatures and extended sea ice cover towards North although their wide presence suggests some resilience to extreme conditions (Krause-Jensen et al., 2012; Thyrring et al., 2021). This pattern is supported by trends in other Arctic regions (Krause-Jensen et al., 2020) and by macroalgal physiology, with the dominant Arctic species having a boreal

origin with optimum temperatures far beyond those in the Arctic region (Müller et al., 2009).

Opposite to what we expected, the macroalgal taxa richness in Qeqertarsuup Tunua continued to decline despite the ending of the Little Ice Age around 1850 CE and the onset of recent global warming. In addition, brown algae, which are regarded as the most relevant macroalgal C donors to sediment C sequestration, and the most prevalent C donors at the core site in Qeqertarsuup Tunua, displayed sequential absence and presence over the recent 100 years combined with very low taxa richness. This suggests that burial of macroalgal-derived C was reduced in that period compared to previous periods. We speculate that this may be related to Qeqertarsuup Tunua being near the marine terminating glacier. The glacier started breaking off its ice tongue in the early 20th Century and only reached its present configuration, with icebergs calved from a grounded margin, after the break-up of the floating tongue in 2002 (Motyka et al., 2011).

4.3. Limitations of the *sedaDNA* analyses

SedaDNA approaches have limitations and potential biases, which should be considered. Introduction of exogenous DNA and cross contamination while collecting, preparing, and sequencing samples may occur (e.g. Armbrecht et al., 2019). We utilized protocols and controls to minimize the occurrence and effect of contamination. Metabarcoding studies can be affected by PCR bias, which causes some taxa to be amplified more than others (Deagle et al., 2014; Elbrecht and Leese, 2015; Krehenwinkel et al., 2017). We focused on higher taxonomic groups to minimize this bias and, moreover, we focused on the changes in richness rather than number of or presence of specific amplicon sequences. Third, the degradation rate of DNA over long periods of time is not well understood, but we used equimolar concentration of DNA from each sample for sequencing to reduce this bias. Finally, the degradation rate of DNA could depend on the source taxa and state (intra- compared to extracellular DNA) but the effect of this on *sedaDNA* studies is not well understood and is an important avenue for future research.

5. Conclusion

We found strong evidence of widespread burial of macroalgal C, especially from kelps and fucoids, based on their millennial fingerprint (*sedaDNA*) in dated marine sediment cores along the west coast of Greenland (60°N–79°N). Our study thereby highlights prevalent burial of macroalgae in Arctic marine sediments over time-scales relevant for C sequestration and provides the first historical archive of macroalgal DNA in sedimentary Arctic deposits combined with climate variables. Although the occurrence of macroalgal orders in the sediments was common over the past 1000–2600 years, our data did not allow quantification of the contribution of macroalgae to the sediment organic C pool. We identified no consistent changes in the presence-absence of macroalgal taxa down through the sediments in response to the environmental changes over time assessed from sediment proxies, and no clear latitudinal pattern in buried macroalgal DNA. However, at Qeqertarsuup Tunua in the Disko Bay, taxa richness of buried macroalgal DNA declined over the past 800 years, coinciding partially with greater environmental fluctuations and changes in glacial configuration of the nearby marine terminating glacier triggered by the Little Ice Age. We hope these novel findings will encourage further developments and finer resolution of *sedaDNA* to fingerprint macroalgae as a source of organic C in marine sediments and develop assays to quantify the contribution of the identified key species to C storage.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sarah B. Ørberg: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marit-Solveig**

Seidenkrantz: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nathan R. Gerald:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation. **Camilla S. Andresen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Kasper Urup Kjeldsen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources. **Carlos M. Duarte:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Dorte Krause-Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

We have nothing to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.180191>.

Data availability

The raw data underlying the main results of the study will be archived at PANGAEA (www.pangaea.de)

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